

ISic0057

I.Sicily inscription 0057

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Q(uintus) · Fabius · Q(uinti) · I(ibertus)
2. Isio
3. Laeliae · D(ecimi) · I(ibertae) · Coprillae
4. uxori

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285311

EDR 127541

EDCS 22100105

Bibliography

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